

Levels of self-efficacy and adjustment among Filipino elementary teachers in the re-opening of face-to-face classes

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ABSTRACT

The learning community has been profoundly affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. In the Philippines, Filipino teachers faced challenges such as adjustment to new pedagogical concepts, styles of delivery, and different environments due to the limitations imposed by the nationwide lockdown. The Department of Education (DepEd) shifted promptly to switch to online learning and develop the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP). This plan outlines how education will continue during the pandemic, with a primary focus on protecting the well-being and safety of students, instructors, and staff. Furthermore, the Department of Education mandated the return of five days of in-person classes two years later, when education had recovered to normal, following the effects of COVID-19. The aim of this study is to describe the levels of teachers' self-efficacy, adjustment, and the relationship between these variables when the reopening to five-day face-to-face classes was implemented. The respondents of the study were teachers from Beata Elementary School at Pandacan, Manila. A correlational method was used to perform the research. The researchers utilized a survey questionnaire that included the Teachers' Sense of Efficacy Scale (TSES), created by Megan Tschannen-Moran and Anita Woolfolk Hoy in 2001, as well as the Teachers' Adjustment Scale developed by the researchers. Data revealed that there is a high level of self-efficacy ($\bar{x}=8.04$) and adjustment ($x=8.38$) among the Filipino elementary teachers. The study revealed a positive correlation between self-efficacy and teacher adjustment, indicating that the higher the level of self-efficacy, the higher the level of teacher adjustment.

ARTICLE INFO

Received : May 1, 2023

Revised : Dec. 11, 2023

Accepted : Dec. 30, 2023

KEYWORDS

Face-to-face classes, Filipino elementary teachers adjustment, Reopening of classes, Self-efficacy

Suggested Citation (APA Style 7th Edition):

Dellomos, C.O., Dela Cruz, M.A.D., Martinez, S., Miciano, K.N.L., Tiongson, R.J.C., Ty, J.M., Faylona, M.G.P.G., Tumaob, J.M.M., Tan, S.G., & Castro, B.M. (2023). Levels of self-efficacy and adjustment among Filipino elementary teachers in the re-opening of face-to-face classes. *International Research Journal of Science, Technology, Education, and Management*, 3(4), 166-179.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10516518>

INTRODUCTION

The worldwide impact of the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly influenced the field of education. The existing crisis has underscored the deficiencies in our educational systems, revealing issues such as restricted availability of computers and internet bandwidth for online learning, as well as the absence of a conducive environment for both educators and students to focus (OECD, 2020). To illustrate the severity of the situation, 14 nations experienced a near-total loss of classroom instruction time (UNICEF, 2021). According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (2020), the global closure of educational institutions has adversely affected more than 1.2 billion students, with over 28 million learners in the Philippines alone. Moreover, educators faced numerous challenges during this sudden transition, including supporting their students' development (Sindhya, 2022), grappling with a lack of internet access (Tosun et al., 2021), and contending with parents with insufficient academic involvement and lower socioeconomic status (Caraan et al., 2022).

In the Philippines, educators commonly face challenges related to the effective use of information communications technology (ICT) and the availability of free tools and resources (Bautista Jr., 2021). To address these issues and ensure the uninterrupted delivery of high-quality education amid the COVID-19 pandemic, the Department of Education (DepEd) established the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP). This initiative aims not only to facilitate learning through online platforms but also to prioritize the well-being of teachers, students, and other members of the school community. Despite the swift transition from traditional classrooms to virtual learning environments, the resulting closures significantly impacted teachers. They had to adapt to new pedagogical concepts and teaching methods, often without prior training (OECD, 2020). Furthermore, upon returning to physical classrooms, teachers encountered diverse settings, procedures, and instructional approaches (Pressley & Ha, 2021). These challenges compelled educators to adopt innovative instructional techniques (Honigsfeld & Nordmeyer, 2020) and necessitated their incorporation of new technological platforms (Wiggins, 2020).

Given the variety of new challenges and evolving regulations encountered by teachers, it is crucial that they comprehend the effects that these have. The apparent scarcity of research on school reopening methods and strategies, especially in the Philippines, contributes to our limited comprehension of the effects of teachers returning to classes in person. Thus, this study aims to explore how shifting teaching methods and learning delivery modalities have affected Filipino elementary teachers' self-efficacy and adjustment.

Holzberger et al. (2013) characterize teacher self-efficacy (TSE) as an individual's confidence in their ability to teach students effectively, even in the face of challenges. Poulou et al. (2019) demonstrated that prior to the pandemic, educators generally possessed high levels of self-efficacy in instructional domains. However, the onset of the global health crisis introduced new challenges for teachers. The rapid adjustments required in teaching methods had a significant impact on their self-efficacy (Andreou et al., 2022). Pressley and Ha (2021) discovered that elementary school teachers in the United States faced reduced levels of instructional and engagement efficacy during the pandemic. Nevertheless, few studies have explored the effects of COVID-19 on TSE beyond the context of online instruction (Andreou et al., 2022). To address this gap, empirical studies on self-efficacy among elementary school science teachers in El Salvador City (Bug-os, 2021) and Cagayan De Oro (Walag, 2021) were conducted, both yielding positive outcomes. In a related study, Leonardo and Cha (2021) found that science teachers with high self-efficacy were better equipped to maintain their composure and overcome challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Studies have found that TSE improves their effectiveness (Hussain & Khan, 2022; Seghal et al., 2017). The results corroborate the claims offered by Morris et al. (2017), who argue that TSE is a subjective indicator of teachers' abilities to perform teaching activities. Garvis and Pendergast (2016) also found that self-efficacy improves in-service teachers' effectiveness by making them more committed, enthusiastic, determined, resilient, understanding of less successful students, willing to try new methods and innovative ideas, use hands-on methods of instruction, and be more organized. UNESCO (2020) recommends that everyone participate in shaping education's future (UNESCO, 2020). The resumption of face-to-face lessons in the Philippines, which has yielded limited or no improvement,

highlights the necessity for more investigation into teacher self-efficacy as a construct, despite the current state of research on this topic.

In the context of this study, adjustment is characterized as "a modification in an individual's attitude, behavior, or both, prompted by a recognized need or desire to change, especially to address the present environment or a changing, atypical, or unexpected situation" (APA Dictionary of Psychology, 2015). Numerous research investigations have explored teacher adjustment utilizing diverse factors. In the current study, the term pertains to the individual efforts made by teachers to adapt in response to the resumption of fully in-person classes.

The COVID-19 pandemic impacted education. Shi and Wu (2021) stated that educators have to change their teaching techniques, resources, and assessment methods to adapt to changing circumstances. They needed to change their mindset and make learning flexible (Alhawsawi and Jawhar, 2021), learn to use technology (Arena et al., 2021), know their learners better to promote learning (Bishop, 2021), and adjust their teaching strategies and time management to meet curriculum requirements (Jackaria, 2022). In these changing times, well-managed virtual and face-to-face classrooms must foster student participation to create school connectivity (Center for Disease Control and Prevention, 2021). As shown in Muhammad et al.'s (2022) study, teachers are required to innovate their class management by developing interesting activities for students, strengthening interpersonal interactions with them, and creating competitive assessments.

According to the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) (2017), teachers are considered lifelong learners as their past approaches may not be directly applicable in the present context (Dos Santos et al., 2017). Recognizing the new challenges faced by educators, it becomes crucial to consider the adjustments made by teachers. Consequently, experts have initiated examinations into the impact of transitioning from various distance learning methods to traditional in-person classes on teachers' confidence levels. This assessment encompasses their belief in their ability to effectively carry out individual or institutional tasks, alongside the personal actions taken by teachers to adapt in anticipation of the resumption of face-to-face classes. Given the significant link between self-efficacy and adjustment, it is imperative to evaluate the levels of these constructs. This inquiry has the potential to guide educators and school administrators in crafting targeted policies and initiatives aimed at enhancing the self-efficacy of elementary school teachers in the Philippines.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The objective of this study was to determine the levels of self-efficacy and their relationship with the levels of adjustment among the teachers at Beata Elementary School. The researchers specifically aimed to study the following questions:

1. Identify the levels of self-efficacy among the teachers of Beata Elementary School during the full implementation of face-to-face classes.
2. Identify levels of adjustment among the teachers of Beata Elementary School during the full implementation of face-to-face classes.
3. Identify the relationship between the levels of self-efficacy and adjustment among Beata Elementary School.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

A descriptive-correlational approach was utilized to collect quantitative data from the population. This was done to describe the existing relationship between two variables - teachers' self-efficacy and adjustment.

Respondents and Locale of the Study

This research was done at Beata Elementary School, a public school located at Pandacan, Manila. The researchers chose this location as it is currently one of the community extension partners of the Faculty of Behavioral and Social Sciences of Philippine Normal University-Manila where extension programs are being conducted, and in which the current study may be of use especially since they are currently in the face-to-face learning modality. The participants were 45 public school teachers under basic education who qualified in the inclusion criteria set by the researchers. Specifically, (a) a licensed professional teacher, (b) is currently employed as an elementary teacher at a local public elementary school, (c) has a teaching experience of at least 1-5 years, (d) and is currently teaching at least one elementary subject.

Table 1a. Biological Sex and Age of Elementary Teachers

Biological Sex and Age	f	%
Female	40	88.89
21-25	3	6.67
26-30	5	11.11
31-35	4	8.89
36-40	7	15.56
41-45	10	22.22
46-50	5	11.11
51-55	1	2.22
56-60	5	11.11
Male	5	11.11
26-30	2	4.44
31-35	2	4.44
36-40	1	2.22
Total	45	100.00

Table 1a shows that out of the 52 elementary teachers from Beata Elementary School, 45 were able to answer the survey-questionnaires. Based on the data, most of the respondents are female ages 41-45 years old.

Table 1b. Years of Teaching of Elementary Teachers

Years of Teaching	Female		Male		Grand Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
1-5	8	17.78	2	4.44	10	22.22
6-10	5	11.11	2	4.44	7	15.56
11-15	9	20.00	1	2.22	10	22.22
16-20	10	22.22			10	22.22
21-25	1	2.22			1	2.22
26-30	2	4.44			2	4.44
31-35	5	11.11			5	11.11
Grand Total	40	88.89	5	11.11	45	100.00

Table 1b shows the years of teaching of the respondents and majority have been in service for 16-20 years. Based on the data, there are similarities in the grand total of the teaching ranges between 1-5 years, 11-15 years, and 16-20 years in their teaching field, while the majority of them are female.

Table 1c. Subjects Taught and Grade Level Handled of Elementary Teachers

Subjects Taught	Grade Level Handled														Grand Total	
	Grade 1		Grade 2		Grade 3		Grade 4		Grade 5		Grade 6		Kinder garten			
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Araling Panlipunan			1	2.22	1	2.22	1	2.22	1	2.22	1	2.22			5	11.11
Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (EsP)					1	2.22					1	2.22			2	4.44
Edukasyong Pantahanan at Pangkabuhayan (EPP)							1	2.22	3	6.67	1	2.22			5	11.11
English			1	2.22	1	2.22	1	2.22	1	2.22	1	2.22			5	11.11
Filipino	3	6.67	1	2.22	1	2.22	1	2.22	1	2.22	1	2.22			8	17.78
Kindergarten subjects													3	6.67	3	6.67
MAPEH (Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health)					1	2.22			1	2.22					2	4.44
Math	3	6.67	1	2.22	1	2.22	1	2.22	1	2.22	1	2.22			8	17.78
Mother Tongue – Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE)			2	4.44	1	2.22									3	6.67
Science					1	2.22	1	2.22	1	2.22	1	2.22			4	8.89
Grand Total	6	13.33	6	13.33	8	17.78	6	13.33	9	20.00	7	15.56	3	2.22	45	100.00

Table 1c illustrates that Filipino and Mathematics are the most frequent subjects taught by the majority of teachers in Grade 1. While the majority of the elementary teachers are handling Grade 5 students and teaching Edukasyong Pantahanan at Pangkabuhayan (EPP) as the most frequent subject.

Research Instrument

The Teachers' Sense of Efficacy Scale (TSES) was constructed during a seminar at The Ohio State University's College of Education in 2001 by Tschannen-Moran and Hoy. The researchers explored various measurement approaches, including a Likert-type scale and an extended scale suggested by Bandura. Three separate studies investigated the newly developed measure, referred to as the Ohio State teacher efficacy scale (OSTES). Originally comprising 52 items, it was reduced to 32 in the initial study and further streamlined to 18 items categorized into three subscales in the second study: instructional strategies, classroom management, and student engagement. Additional scrutiny led to the creation of 18 more items that were subsequently assessed.

The final instrument had two varieties: a 24-item long form and a 12-item short form. Lastly, an analysis of the new measure's factor structure, reliability, and validity, was done as well as its suitability for both preservice and in-service teacher populations. (Tschannen-Moran, M., & Hoy, A., 2001).

Furthermore, to measure teachers' levels of adjustment, the researchers examined the seven domains outlined in the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). The seven domains of the PPST and their 37 strands were clustered based on their similarities and relevance to each other. In the process of item construction, the researchers constructed questions based on career stage two of the PPST and identified constructs, which are as follows: pedagogical practices, classroom management and personal and professional development. From this, 61 items were created to measure the adjustment of teachers. A scale ranging from 9 (regularly) to 1 (rarely) was used

for each item. Lastly, the researchers sought content and construct validations from experts for this Teachers' Adjustment Scale. The validators approved all 61 items, which were thus included in the data collection process.

Data Collection

The potential link between teachers' self-efficacy and their adjustments in the re-opening of face-to-face classes was investigated using a quantitative methodology. The method used produced generalizable results about elementary teachers' self-efficacy and adjustment during the reopening of face-to-face classes. Before sending the survey questionnaire to Beata Elementary School teachers, the researchers got approval from the principal. After contacting every necessary organization, the researchers used Google Forms to conduct an online survey that respondents could complete at any point during the gathering of data. The data privacy consent form, Teachers' Sense of Efficacy Scale, and Teachers' Adjustment Scale, along with instructions, has been included in each survey questionnaire.

Data Analysis

The data were collected through survey questionnaires through Google Forms and were transferred to a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet for quantitative analysis. The population's self-efficacy level was ascertained by calculating the mean and standard deviation of the overall self-efficacy variable and its subscales. Such calculations were also employed with the teachers' adjustment variable. Thereafter, the numerical ranges were derived from the variables' means and standard deviations, and adjectival interpretations for both variables and their corresponding subscales were developed. Finally, using the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficients via JASP software, and p-values of the two variables and their subscales were examined. This was done after organizing the necessary data for teachers' self-efficacy and adjustment. Every correlation's p-value reveals the degree of significance associated with each correlation coefficient.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers sent a formal letter to the school administration asking for permission to conduct the study. Similar letters were also sent to the administration for teacher respondents prior to the actual survey-questionnaire administration. The researcher obtained consent from the teacher respondents through the research instrument in Google Forms to demonstrate their voluntary participation in this study. Finally, only the researchers had access to the Google Forms and Sheets containing responses for the protection of each respondent's information.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 Levels of Elementary Teachers' Self-Efficacy

Teacher's Self-Efficacy Subscales	Mean n=45	Standard Deviation	Adjectival Interpretation
Student Engagement	8.03	0.57	High
Instructional Strategies	8.00	0.70	High
Classroom Management	8.08	0.69	High
Grand Total	8.04	0.65	High

te: 1.0 – 3.0 Low Self-efficacy, 3.1 – 7.0 Average Self-efficacy, 7.1 – 9.0 High Self-efficacy

The average and standard deviation from the gathered responses suggest that the 45 elementary educators in the study demonstrated a heightened level of self-efficacy ($\bar{x} = 8.04$) when confronting the challenges posed by the resumption of face-to-face classes. According to Bandura (1997) and Garvis & Tekin (2016), self-efficacy is defined as an individual's beliefs and judgments regarding their capability to handle and successfully perform essential tasks. In the context of teaching, self-efficacy emerges as a pivotal motivational factor, instilling teachers with confidence

in their capacity to carry out tasks proficiently. This study specifically delved into self-efficacy by examining student engagement, instructional strategies, and classroom management as distinct subscales.

The self-efficacy of the 45 elementary teachers appears to be high ($\bar{x}=8.03$) in connection with engagement from students in the re-opening of face-to-face classes. This implies that the respondents' personal belief that they can do well in handling the difficult situations that involve students inside the classroom reflects on how the respondents think critically by being creative in motivating the students and helping them do well in school which results in improving the students' value for learning. This supports the study of Muhammad et. al. (2022) that teachers need to innovate how they manage their class by creating engaging activities for students, strengthening interpersonal relationships with them, as well as creating assessments that promote their competitiveness. However, this result contradicts a previous study of Gale et al. (2021), where they claimed that the level of self-efficacy among educators with more experience was higher for instructional methods and managing classrooms but not for engagement from students.

In addition, the primary school educators exhibit a notable degree of confidence ($\bar{x} = 8.00$) when it comes to employing instructional approaches during the resumption of in-person classes. This signifies that the survey participants personally feel capable of employing various teaching methods to facilitate effective student learning. This involves acquiring expertise on the subject matter, making necessary preparations, and customizing instructional tools and materials while considering students' learning requirements and preferences. Research by Künsting et al. (2016) indicates that educators with high self-efficacy levels are more inclined to endorse and implement innovative instructional methods and tools that cater to students' needs. This finding aligns with the perspectives of Bug-os et al. (2021) and Naureen & Shahzad (2017), highlighting the crucial role of teachers' strong self-efficacy in shaping students' educational experiences. Such influence is exerted through teachers' confidence, presentation of diverse ideas, and the integration of inventive teaching techniques, as opposed to rigid adherence to conventional methods of instruction.

This result also shows progress compared to a recent study conducted by Pressley & Ha (2021) which highlighted that when the COVID-19 pandemic hit the education system and new challenges occurred, teachers' self-efficacy was affected resulting in the decline in terms of instructional and engagement efficacy. Furthermore, a high level of self-efficacy ($\bar{x}=8.08$) manifests in terms of classroom management. Well-managed classrooms in both virtual and face-to-face need to promote student engagement to build school connectedness more than ever (Center for Disease Control and Prevention, 2021). Moreover, proper classroom management improves student performance and behaviour (Mitchell, 2019; Simonsen et al., 2013). Self-efficacious individuals recover from difficulties more rapidly than those with low self-efficacy. This implies that, with regard to classroom management, teachers who lack self-efficacy in their capability to address disruptions effectively are less likely to intervene in an effort to resolve such matters (Dicke et al., 2014). Furthermore, educators can achieve greater effectiveness in the context of inclusive classrooms by implementing collaborative practices, employing effective pedagogical approaches, and efficiently managing disruptive behaviors (Mitchell, 2019; Sharma et al., 2012).

Table 3 Levels of Elementary Teachers' Adjustment

Teacher's Adjustment Subscales	Mean n=45	Standard Deviation	Adjectival Interpretation
Pedagogical Practices	8.20	0.74	High
Classroom Management	8.47	0.61	High
Personal and Professional Development	8.46	0.65	High
Grand Total	8.38	0.67	High

Note: 1.0 – 3.0 Low Adjustment, 3.1 – 7.0 Average Adjustment, 7.1 – 9.0 High Adjustment

The data reveal that the 45 elementary teachers have a high level of adjustment ($\bar{x}=8.38$) in the re-opening of in-person classes, after determining the standard deviation and average level of the responses. In this research, to determine the levels of adjustment of the respondents, three subscales namely pedagogical practices, classroom management, and personal and professional development were measured. In terms of pedagogical practices, a high level of adjustment ($\bar{x}=8.20$) manifests among the elementary teachers during the re-opening of face-to-face classes. This implies that the elementary teachers took personal actions to adapt in lieu of the re-opening of face-to-face classes. The importance of pedagogical practices was further corroborated by the research of Bixuan et. al., (2020), which highlighted how this can influence not only how students learn but also how they can be engaged in schooling.

As the Center for Disease Control and Prevention (2021) notes, it is crucial that during these changing times, well-managed classrooms in both virtual and face-to-face need to promote student engagement to build school connectedness. This was evident in the findings of this paper, manifesting that elementary teachers are highly adjusted ($\bar{x}=8.47$) in terms of classroom management. With the recent implementation of DepEd Order 034, it is mandated that both private and public schools must transition to five-day in-person classes. Thus, the educational system is expected to adjust their classroom management and the learning delivery modality. A teachers' personal and professional development is an important aspect of their life and this was apparent from this paper's results, which reveals that elementary teachers possess a high degree of adjustment ($\bar{x}=8.46$). In an effort to improve the educational system, it is evident that respondents would be expected to treat themselves as both experts in their subject and lifelong learners. This can be reasoned out by the PPST (2017), where teachers are lifelong learners due to the fact that their prior methods cannot be replicated in the present context (Dos Santos et. al., 2017). Thus, personal and professional development also contributes to the teachers' effectiveness. Consequently, the three subscales all contribute to improving the teachers' level of adjustment and their personal actions being taken to adapt in lieu of the re-opening of face-to-face classes.

Table 4 Relationship of Teachers' Self-Efficacy and Adjustment

Teacher's Self-Efficacy	Teacher's Adjustment			
	Pedagogical Practices	Classroom Management	Personal and Professional Development	Total Teacher's Adjustment
Student Engagement	0.597**	0.541**	0.541**	0.596**
Instructional Strategies	0.577**	0.523**	0.544**	0.583**
Classroom Management	0.537**	0.463*	0.530**	0.543**
Total Self-Efficacy	0.628**	0.559**	0.594**	0.632**

*Note: *p < .01, **p < .001*

Table 4 illustrates the association between teacher self-efficacy and adjustment among 45 elementary school teachers. The study identified a positive correlation ($r = 0.623$) between teachers' self-efficacy and adjustment. As the level of teachers' self-efficacy ($\bar{x} = 8.04$) increases, there is a corresponding increase in their adjustment ($\bar{x} = 8.38$). This discovery aligns with Maddux's (1995) assertion that self-efficacy beliefs contribute to psychological adjustment by influencing factors such as perseverance and goal-setting, emotional flexibility, and cognitive efficiency.

Elaborating on such findings, the subscales of teachers' self-efficacy and adjustment justify their positive correlation. For instance, there is a positive correlation ($r = 0.597$) between pedagogical practices and teachers' student engagement. Hence, as the level of student engagement in teachers' self-efficacy increases ($\bar{x}=8.03$), the level of pedagogical practices in teachers' adjustment increases ($\bar{x}=8.20$) as well. Likewise, the student engagement is positively associated with both classroom management ($r=0.541$) and personal and professional development ($r=0.541$) subscales of teachers' adjustment. These mean that the higher the teacher's self-efficacy on student engagement ($\bar{x}=8.03$), the higher their levels of classroom management ($\bar{x}=8.47$) and personal and professional development ($\bar{x}=8.46$) subscales.

Furthermore, there exists a positive correlation ($r=0.577$, $p<.001$) between the instructional strategies subscale of teachers' self-efficacy and the pedagogical practices subscale of teachers' adjustment. It indicates that the greater the level of the teachers' instructional strategies ($\bar{x}=8.00$), the greater their level of pedagogical practices ($\bar{x}=8.20$). Similarly, the same subscale of instructional strategies has a positive relation with the two remaining subscales of teachers' adjustment, namely, classroom management ($r=0.523$, $p<.001$) and personal and professional development ($r=0.544$, $p<.001$). Therefore, the levels of classroom management ($\bar{x}=8.47$) and personal and professional development ($\bar{x}=8.46$) rise as the level of instructional strategies ($\bar{x}=8.00$) does

Third, regarding the last subscale of teachers' self-efficacy, which is classroom management, this study found that it has a positive association with the two subscales of teachers' adjustment: pedagogical practices ($r=0.537$, $p<.001$) and personal and professional development ($r=0.530$, $p<.001$). With these data, it is established that teachers' adjustments in terms of pedagogical practices ($\bar{x}=8.08$), personal and professional development ($\bar{x}=8.20$), and classroom management effectiveness all increase as ($\bar{x}=8.08$) and ($\bar{x}=8.20$) respectively. However, it is significant to acknowledge that the classroom management subscales of teachers' self-efficacy and adjustment exhibit the lowest level of positive correlation ($r=0.463$, $p<.01$) among all the subscales. This infers that efficacy in classroom management ($\bar{x}=8.08$) is positively correlated to classroom management ($\bar{x}=8.47$) of teachers' adjustment on average.

Hence, a positive relationship was discovered between the entirety of teachers' self-efficacy and each subscale of teachers' adjustment, which are pedagogical practices ($r=0.628$, $p<.001$), classroom management ($r=0.559$, $p<.001$), personal and professional development ($r=0.594$, $p<.001$). This may be interpreted as the level of teachers' self-efficacy ($\bar{x}=8.04$) increases, so do the subscales of pedagogical practices ($\bar{x}=8.20$), classroom management ($\bar{x}=8.47$), and personal and professional development ($\bar{x}=8.46$). Despite a two-year distance learning approach in the Philippines, it is worth noting that teachers at Beata Elementary School have a positive correlation between self-efficacy and adjustment during the full implementation of face-to-face classes.

However, the results of this research are deemed satisfactory. The complete rollout of face-to-face classes at Beata Elementary School unveiled elevated levels of self-efficacy among teachers. Consequently, participants also demonstrated heightened levels of adjustment, affirming a positive correlation between teachers' self-efficacy and adjustment.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

A frequently observed crucial factor influencing teaching effectiveness is teachers' self-efficacy, as it serves as a potent motivator influencing their classroom behavior and dedication (Klassen and Tze, 2014; Klassen et al., 2009; Barni, 2019). Additionally, Tripathy's 2019 study revealed that well-adjusted teachers tend to deliver superior and higher-quality instruction while managing student issues more effectively. Following two years of exclusive distance learning, the Department of Education (DepEd) opted to reintroduce full face-to-face instruction, reconfiguring the recent developments brought about by distance learning in the Philippine education system. The research findings highlight that during the complete implementation of face-to-face classes at Beata Elementary School, teachers demonstrated a high level of self-efficacy (mean = 8.04) and adjustment (mean = 8.38). Delving into these findings, a robust and positive correlation was identified between the two variables and their respective subscales concerning self-efficacy and adjustment levels. This implies that a higher degree of adjustment among Filipino elementary school teachers corresponds to a stronger level of self-efficacy, and vice versa.

Measuring the self-efficacy and adjustment levels of teachers provides us with the new knowledge that the teachers from Beata Elementary School were able to adapt to the changes that happened with the reopening of face-to-face classes. In accordance with this, it is therefore recommended that, for the Beata Elementary School teachers, they have a dialogue with the administration and be part of training and programs that enhance teaching pedagogy to sustain their adjustment and self-efficacy degrees. Regarding the administration of Beata Elementary School and Schools Division of Manila, programs, policies and initiatives that enhance the sense of authority of teachers to improve classroom management skills. Finally, for future researchers, considering that this study only discussed the

self-efficacy and adjustment levels of elementary teachers at Beata Elementary School, they can consider conducting further studies in a different locality or region and among secondary and even college-level teachers. They may also include gender and the teachers' socioeconomic standing as moderating or mediating variables.

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